
INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING TECHNICAL TERMINOLOGY IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna

Karshi engineering - economics Institute,

Senior lecturer at Foreign Languages Department

badalovaluiza8@gmail.com

Abstract.

The introduction of innovations in all branches of science and technology, the requirements for automating the transmission and processing of information in various areas of human activity lead to the emergence of new terminological units and, as a result, an increase in the importance of terminology as a means of acquiring and organizing scientific knowledge. The article discusses innovative methods of teaching technical terminology in non-linguistic universities and some features of their use in teaching a foreign language in technical universities.

Keywords.

communication, professional, technical specialties, terminology, methods.

Introduction:

Modern specialists should have the knowledge, skills and abilities of business communication, have an idea about the organizational structure of the business world, the norms of business etiquette, in particular, in an intercultural context. Techniques and methods for teaching terminology in English are currently little developed. The problem is that a student of a technical university cannot study all the disciplines according to the program of special technical universities and compete with their knowledge with specialists in a particular field of activity [1,174]. The special knowledge of an engineer with knowledge of a foreign language must be of a very special kind. Especially relevant is the training of students of technical specialties of terminology, since without sufficient knowledge of it, it is impossible to penetrate into any special field of activity and provide various forms of interlingual communication in the field of business communication [2, 14].

According to V. M. Leichik, "the intellectualization of the language recognized by many scientists is connected to a large extent with the widespread use of special

vocabulary in it" [17, 20]. Scientists have calculated that over 80% of all new vocabulary in modern languages are special lexical units (17, 20).

Main part:

Among the wide variety, we will consider the most productive methods for teaching technical specialists, based on the practice of working in a technical university when training specialists in the field of oil and gas industry. There are several methods for teaching future terminology specialists. Over time, some of them become obsolete and new ones come to replace them. The choice of methods determines the correspondence with the following pedagogical concepts: communicative approach; approach to problem solving; professional orientation in teaching foreign languages; learning-oriented approach. Ideally, the educational process should be based on a carefully considered combination of teaching methods [1,176].

One of the widely used methods is the case method, in which students analyze real economic, social and business situations. Students must understand the situation, suggest possible solutions and choose the best one. Cases are based either on real factual material, or close to the real situation. Students are usually given a text of thematic content up to two pages, including introductory information, a description of the event or problem, as well as questions for group discussion.

This method is proposed to be used with advanced level students for whom communication in a foreign language is not particularly difficult. Some errors in pronunciation and grammar are acceptable, which do not affect the understanding of the material under discussion as a whole. The case method includes: free discussions, directed discussions, group research work, written assignments and other activities (5, p. 88). During the practical use of this method in the process of studying terminology on the topic "Coal strip mine", students were offered two texts for reading and translation, which were accompanied by a list of terms with explanations and comments. Students more accurately understood and correctly used the studied vocabulary after working with texts in which the practical use of terms is clearly visible. To consolidate the result, a discussion of the material read was organized based on the questions of the teacher.

Another method is to create presentations. This method is an important component in teaching a foreign language; it develops oratory and public speaking skills. It is also a good way to develop speaking and discussion skills. Engineering students need the skills to present information and coaching in their future jobs. Therefore, they should be taught instructive and demonstrative speeches and presentations, followed by discussion. While working on a presentation, students

master the skills of recording key concepts, phrases, quotes, brief textual information and printing it on slides. The task of the teacher is to check and, if necessary, correct the existing errors, to direct students to memorize difficult words. When getting acquainted with new information, images on the screen allow students to associate a phrase in a foreign language directly with an object or action. The colorful pictures, diagrams, animated images seen on the screen contribute to a better perception and assimilation of new material [6,130]. The process of working on the creation of each individual slide is built as a process of solving increasingly complex speech-thinking tasks that require intellectual search efforts from students. Work continues on the formation of sustainable interest and motivation for the further study of a foreign language. Working on a presentation develops students' imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personality traits. All this reflects the developmental aspect of learning. After students have presented their presentation to the audience, they should be able to provide additional comments and answer questions as needed [9, 3518]. Using visual aids as a support, the student speaks on professional, specific topics, providing listeners with deeper knowledge and a clearer understanding of the material being presented. Years of experience in a technical university shows that a presentation can last 4-5 minutes, but in some of the most advanced groups, students themselves vote for a limit of 8-10 minutes. Advanced level students are happy to join the discussion, demonstrating knowledge of certain material in their specialty and practicing the use of the studied terminology in the process of discussion. For non-fluent students, this is a great opportunity to immerse yourself in the language environment and strive to improve your language skills. This method is used by teachers to complete the work on the theme. Students are divided into mini-groups of two or three people, while we recommend that strong students be combined with weak ones. When preparing for a presentation, stronger students can act as mentors, help those who are lagging behind prepare slide material and work through a large amount of literature. Such work shows in practice that students not only improve their language skills, but also begin to better understand professional issues.

And the last of the most commonly used methods is group training, which includes a wide range of activities. The term "group learning" comes from the Western practice of higher education, where this approach to learning has been used for a long time. American professor L. Trump introduced this method of work in the 50-60s of the twentieth century [7, 1635]. One of the specific forms that has

become widespread in recent years is the teaching of one discipline by two teachers.

This method was used when a lesson was conducted jointly by a native speaker, an expert engineer or just a local oil and gas specialist and a teacher of a group of students. A native speaker or local expert shares professional knowledge with students, and the teacher organizes the work of students in the lesson, directs and coordinates, and helps to explain difficult moments for students, if any. Students enjoy such activities, prepare for them more carefully so that they can not only listen, but also ask questions and express their opinions. Thus, the motivation of students is growing, and as a result, the general language level and the level of terminology proficiency are growing. The benefits for students when using this method are undeniable. For educators, this practice also brings many benefits. In preparation for classes, the professional level rises and the methodological outlook expands. Group learning methods can be different. Both educators work, the other supervises. It is also possible to divide the group into subgroups, during the training of which certain topics are considered under the guidance of teachers. With such a division, one teacher works with the stronger part of the group, the other with the lagging students.

Successful group learning can be beneficial for both teachers and students. Teachers get the opportunity to develop professionally, and students gain valuable experience not only in mastering the terminology in their specialty, but also in the ability to build professional relationships on simulated situations. Group learning requires careful planning and preparation. In this case, some rules and requirements must be observed:

- 1) The teacher must be flexible in the process of planning and teaching;
- 2) Teachers should be able to cooperate, have a spirit of conciliation and a commitment to joint practice;
- 3) Teachers should have equal status and responsibility, regardless of their age, experience and education;
- 4) Teachers should have a common goal and joint coordination of activities.

Conclusion: The advantages of the above teaching methods are numerous, and their use contributes to the development of students' oral and written skills in mastering the terminology of the specialty being studied [11, 73]. Teaching a foreign language should not take place separately from the formation of the professional competence of a future specialist. Foreign language tools are designed to provide a solid language platform and serve as an incentive for career advancement.

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